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Market and Technology Readiness Level methodology and assessments V2

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Abstract:	This report will focus on the progress in the MTRL methodology as well as project self-assessments and progress through the stages of market and technology readiness. This deliverable also includes description about the webinars conducted on the MTRL methodology and its efficacy as well as understanding the assessment criteria made available by the self-assessment form. This report also contains the results from the assessments and how it has helped the projects meet their project goals.
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Terms and abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MRL	Market Readiness Levels
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
MTRL	Market and Technology Readiness Levels
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community

Executive Summary

Within this deliverable of the SWForum.eu project we discuss the Marketing and Technology Readiness Level (MTRL) approach to product assessment and its application within the SWForum.eu set of supported projects to understand how we may improve their competitiveness as described in one of our key project objectives:

Provide guidance for increasing the competitiveness of European initiatives through the definition of a methodological approach to the improvement of their MTRL, Mentoring, Technology Transfer & Best Practices guiding towards Policy Innovation.

We describe in some detail the MTRL methodology including the utilisation of the Market Readiness Level (MRL) and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and how, using automated assessment techniques, we are able to quickly and easily (depending on the engagement of the projects to be assessed themselves) get MTRL assessments completed for projects. This has been assisted through the production of three webinars, two on the overall MTRL assessment framework and one on how to understand the assessment mechanism.

Following this we show the outputs of assessments completed to date and the feedback received from the projects that it facilitates.

Overall, this methodology was successful in assessing the life stages of multiple projects through single and multiple assessments received from the projects. Due to the limited number of projects, however, not all projects were able to submit a reassessment as they had expired over a year ago by the time we conducted a second assessment for the projects. Nonetheless, with over half of the projects submitting at least one assessment, we were successful in meeting our targets.

1 Introduction

Within the SWForum.eu project one of the key objectives of the project is:

Provide guidance for increasing the competitiveness of European initiatives through the definition of a methodological approach to the improvement of their MTRL, Mentoring, Technology Transfer & Best Practices guiding towards Policy Innovation.

This objective aims at defining a methodology to provide guidance to projects to the assessment of their Marketing and Technology Readiness Level (MTRL) and to its consequent improvement, consequently improving the ability of project outputs to be launched to market as successfully as possible. Building on the MTRL methodology designed in the CloudWATCH.eu [1]¹ project which was further tuned in Cyberwatching.eu [3], originally designed to be domain agnostic. We have customized it for the complex problem domain of software engineering, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity. Through the self-assessment tool developed, projects themselves can perform the assessment and receive initial guidance on possible improvements required. Alongside the development of the tool, we have also held three webinars, one introducing at a high level the MTRL methodology and the next two on understanding and assessing the MTRL assessments received. The aim of these webinars was to guide software engineering projects through their MTRL self-assessment journey and provide another tool with which projects can achieve self-improvement.

The first three sections of this document describe the underlying methodology used and the MTRL assessment tool. These are adapted from deliverable D4.4 [9] to maintain consistency and provide context behind assessments and feedback received from projects. This deliverable contains results from the new assessments conducted as well as reassessments from projects that had already submitted a first assessment earlier in their lifecycle. We also received some constructive feedback from projects that shaped how we now look at the MTRL methodology and hope to develop it based on the received feedback.

1.1 Document structure

In Section 2, we describe in detail the MTRL methodology including the utilisation of the Market Readiness Level (MRL) and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and how, using automated assessment techniques, we are able to quickly and easily (depending on the engagement of the projects to be assessed themselves) get MTRL assessments completed for projects.

In Section 3, we describe in detail how the assessment was created and distributed to partners. We explain the questionnaire provided to participants, the formulae and rationale behind calculating the MRL and TRL scores, and ultimately providing recommendations for projects based on their MRL and TRL scores.

In Section 4, we showcase the MTRL assessments conducted so far from 24 projects and their individual scores for each criterion. We also talk about the webinars conducted and how they were useful in getting the MTRL message across to projects.

¹ <http://www.cloudwatchhub.eu/>

2 Methodology

2.1 Measuring the readiness of a product for market launch

One of the most widely used methods to measure the technological maturity of a product or service is the Technology Readiness Level (TRL). Implemented by NASA [2] during the 1980s, this was later formally defined and expanded for use in other industries. At its core, TRL aims to objectively assess the maturity of a technology and classify it against a range of possible points in an idealised product lifecycle, starting with fundamental research and ending with an actual system proven in operational environment. It is now extremely widely used, including by the European Commission Horizon 2020 (H2020) programme.

There are however issues if, you were to use the TRL classification alone, and most particularly for software products as supported by SWForum.eu. We would be unable to confirm the readiness level of a product and/or service to a suitable standard using this one measure in a way that would be useful to the project themselves, since there are further non-technical items that must be considered alongside the technical. Just as technology must be prepared for entry into the market, relevant non-technical factors must be also at a similar level of preparedness. These include support systems and processes, which are increasingly digital, must be available and ready before a product can be sold or a successful service be offered. Moreover, customers must be ready, or enabled to be ready, to acquire and use technology. The gap between pure technology and its preparation for the market must be saved with a better approach.

In the CloudWATCH2 project, this new approach was proposed [3] through the inclusion of an assessment for the Market Readiness Level (MRL) of the outcomes of the cloud-based projects developed under the EU H2020 research program, alongside the Technical Readiness Levels.

This approach aims to give a complete vision of a project both from technical and non-technical points of view. The score obtained by a project according to this methodology is called the **MTRL Score** and it is a combination of the pair of separate inputs TRL & MRL that can be graphically presented to display the status of the project. This representation can be used both to assess the current situation of a project and to design a plan for the future of the project, that is, where we are and where we want to go. Although this approach was thought for the Cloud services domain, it has also been applied to the Cybersecurity and Privacy domain, and we now aim to apply this to the software domains as software has been the key component of those areas where MTRL has been previously applied.

The following sections briefly describe the concepts of TRL and MRL, as they have been used in the scope of this MTRL methodology. This was the basic methodology that will be used for the assessment of projects in the cybersecurity and privacy field by SWForum.eu.

2.2 Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology, as previously mentioned, initially defined by NASA [2]. There are nine technology readiness levels, from TRL 1 the lowest to TRL 9 that is the highest, as represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. NASA Technology Readiness Levels [9]

Using the NASA definition as a starting point, the European Commission (in the H2020 general annexes G [4]) provides the description of the TRL that is applied to EC projects.

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed.
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated.
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept.
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab.
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies).
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies).
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment.
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified.
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space).

As showed in **Error! Reference source not found.**, CloudWATCH2 added a new category "Phase" with several objectives: to simplify the TRL scale in order to keep a limited number of categories; to put more emphasis on and differentiate more between Research (TRL 0 – 3) and Innovation (TRL 4- 5); to recognise industry's need of mature technology which is easier and quicker to develop for market entry.

Table 1. CLOUDWATCH2 Technology Readiness Levels

TRL	Description	Phase
0	Idea. Unproven concept, no testing has been performed.	Idea
1	Basic Research. Principles postulated and observed but no experimental proof available.	
2	Technology formulation. Concept and application have been formulated.	
3	Applied research. First laboratory test completed; proof of concept.	Prototype
4	Small scale prototype. Built in a laboratory environment (early prototype).	
5	Large scale prototype. Tested in intended environment.	Validation
6	Prototype system. Tested in intended environment close to expected performance.	
7	Demonstration system. Operating in operation environment at pre-commercial scale.	Production
8	First of a kind commercial system. Manufacturing issues solved.	
9	Full commercial application. Technology generally available for all consumers.	

2.3 Market Readiness Levels (MRL)

As we already mentioned, although the TRL is a widely used and validated methodology to obtain the state of maturity of a technology, it has certain limitations, especially when determining the readiness for commercialization of that technology.

To bring the results of a project to the market, it is not enough to complete the technological developments, but rather a set of support activities is necessary. This support includes business strategy, business modelling, marketing, sales, after-sales support, etc. And this set of activities must be also measured to accurately determine the readiness level of a project outcome.

It is in this scenario where methodologies, such as Market Readiness Level (MRL), from CloudWATCH2 and Cyberwatching, are applied to better assess the non-technical readiness level of a project output. MRL represents the work performed in the development of business process and administration, as TRL does for technical activities.

Starting from the concept of “business model” as the key mechanics of the product or service brought to market and applying their own “Four Fits Model” [5], CloudWATCH2 defined, as showed in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the MRLs for cloud-centric projects.

Similar to technical product development, MRLs feature four business process-oriented phases, from Ideation to Scaling business to a sustainable – and resilient – commercial operation.

Table 2. CLOUDWATCH2 Market Readiness Levels

MRL	Description	Phase
0	Hunch. You perceive a need within a market and something ignites.	Ideation
1	Basic Research. You can now describe the need(s) but have no evidence.	
2	Needs formulation. You articulate the need(s) using a customer/user story.	
3	Needs validation. You have an initial “offering”; stakeholders like your slideware.	
4	Small scale stakeholder campaign. Run a campaign with stakeholders (“closed” beta – 50 friendly stakeholders).	Testing
5	Large scale early adopter campaign. Run a campaign with early adopters (“open” beta – 100 intended customers).	
6	Proof of traction. Sales match 100 paying customers.	Traction
7	Proof of satisfaction. A happy team and happy customers give evidence to progress.	
8	Proof of scalability. A stable sales pipeline and strong understanding of the market allow revenue projections.	Scaling
9	Proof of stability. KPIs surpassed and predictable growth.	

3 Project Assessment Procedure

As defined in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the evaluation of a project according to the MTRL methodology is done through the evaluation against the pair of measures, TRL and MRL. It is here where we find the main differences between the CloudWatch2 and SWForum.eu methodologies.

SWForum.eu uses a tool that allows to obtain the MTRL, TRL, and MRL scores automatically. The use of an automatic evaluation method provides certain advantages such as:

- Easier accessibility and efficiency to evaluate a large number of projects.
- Standardized, repeatable process for evaluating projects under analysis and review.
- Quick snapshots of the status of a project at a given time allowing creation of timeseries of evaluations.

The MTRL SWForum.eu tool represents each project from relevant calls whose details are available in the SWForum.eu hub.

The evaluation was done with tailored messaging including some recommendations regarding the need for honesty in answering. The results of this auto-evaluation tool to assess the current state of the project, once returned to the SWForum.eu team, were added to the SWForum.eu Radar².

The output of the assessment aims to help the project to identify its own weaknesses and next steps as part of an overall self-evaluation process. Overall, when using this kind of tool, the given score is based only on objective criteria, not being contrasted with the subjective opinion of a team of expert reviewers and, therefore, this provided result should be taken only informatively, so the project representative will be advised not to take any action without having previously consulted with a professional advisor.

In the following sections, we describe the questionnaire that has been used for implementing the MTRL tool and how the scores will be calculated from the answers to get the pair (TRL, MRL).

3.1 SWForum.eu MTRL Tool – The Questionnaire

The NYSEDA TRL Calculator [6] is defined to help emerging and growing companies determine the level of technical and commercial maturity of their products/innovations through the calculation of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and the Commercialisation Readiness Level (CRL). It consists of 7 questions regarding Technology, Product Development, Product Definition / Design, Competitive Landscape, Team, Go-To-Market and Manufacturing / Supply Chain. The Cyberwatching.eu MTRL tool modified these questions and then added two more specifically related to crucial issues when dealing with R&D projects: Documentation and Intellectual Property Management, making 9 questions in total. The first two questions are focused on obtaining a value for the TRL and the rest for the MRL. For each question, 5 possible answers are shown, ordered from less developed (answer number 1) to more developed (answer number 5). The project representative should select the answer that best fits their project. Within SWForum.eu we have not altered the questions or selectable responses from that which was used for Cyberwatching.eu.

Error! Reference source not found. shows the content of the questionnaire (it will also include an introduction and the instructions to fill it). The first sub table gathers general

² <https://radar.swforum.eu/radar/>

information/metadata about the project to be evaluated. Following this are the 9 significant questions for the project assessment.

Table 3. MTRL Questionnaire

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project name	Acronym and full name of the project
Website	The project's website
Full name	The name of the contact person for the project
Email	The contact email address
Project outcomes	A brief description of the expected results of the project, i.e. products, services, components, etc.
Authorization	(A checklist for the user to give permission about certain issues, for example: to publish the results, etc.)
1. PROJECT MATURITY	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project work is beyond basic research and technology concept has been defined 2. Applied research has begun and practical applications have been identified 3. Preliminary testing of technology components has begun in a laboratory environment 4. Initial testing of integrated product has been completed in an operational environment 5. Integrated product demonstrates performance in the intended applications 	
2. PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initial product/market fit has been defined 2. Pilot scale product has been tested in the intended application 3. Demonstration of a full-scale product prototype has been completed in the intended application 4. Actual product has been proven to work in its near-final form under a representative set of expected conditions and environments 5. Product is in final format and has been operated under the full range of operating conditions and environments 	
3. PRODUCT DEFINITION/DESIGN	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. One or more initial product hypotheses have been defined 2. Mapping product attributes against customer needs has highlighted a clear value proposition 3. The product has been scaled from laboratory to pilot scale and issues that may affect achieving full scale have been identified 4. Comprehensive customer value proposition model has been developed, including a detailed understanding of product design specifications, required certifications, and trade-offs 5. Product final design optimization has been completed, required certifications have been obtained and product has incorporated detailed customer and product requirements 	
4. COMPETITIVE LANDSCAPE	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Market research has been performed and basic knowledge of potential applications and competitive landscape have been identified 2. Primary market research to prove the product commercial feasibility has been completed and basic understanding of competitive products has been demonstrated 3. Comprehensive market research to prove the product commercial feasibility has been completed and intermediate understanding of competitive products has been demonstrated 4. Competitive analysis to illustrate unique features and advantages of the product compared to competitive products has been completed 5. Full and complete understanding of the competitive landscape, target applications, competitive products and market has been achieved 	
5. TEAM	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No team or organization (single individual, no legal entity) 2. Solely technical or non-technical founders running the organization with no outside assistance 	

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Solely technical or non-technical founders running the organization with assistance from outside (advisors, mentors, incubator, accelerator, etc.) 4. Balanced team with technical and business experience running the organization 5. Balanced team with all capabilities on-board (sales, marketing, customer service, operations, etc.) running the organization
6. DOCUMENTATION
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Solely technical descriptions have been elaborated, i.e., software documentation, architecture diagrams, etc. 2. User-oriented documentation has been created, such as user manual, installation guides, reference manual, etc. 3. Live demonstration resources have been developed (recorded videos, website with link to demo, etc.) 4. Position papers, press releases, posters, etc. have been elaborated for the dissemination of the project 5. Marketing documentation has been created, such as a Business Model Canvas, etc.
7. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No IPR have been defined 2. Initial means of protection have been considered 3. A proper and clear definition of shares has been elaborated 4. An assignation of exploitation rights has been developed 5. A contractual obligation regarding IPR has been established
8. GO-TO-MARKET
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initial business model and value proposition have been defined 2. Customers have been interviewed to understand their needs and business model and value proposition have been redefined based on customer feedback 3. Market and customer needs and how those translate to product requirements have been defined, and initial relationships have been developed with key stakeholders across the value chain 4. Partnerships have been formed with key stakeholders across the value chain (suppliers, partners, service providers, customers) 5. Supply agreements with suppliers and partners are in place and initial purchase orders from customers have been received
9. MANUFACTURING/SUPPLY CHAIN
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential suppliers, partners and customers have been identified and mapped in an initial value chain analysis 2. Relationships have been established with potential suppliers, partners, service providers and customers and they have provided input on product and manufacturability requirements 3. Manufacturing process qualifications have been defined and are in progress 4. Products have been pilot manufactured and sold to initial customers 5. Full scale manufacturing and widespread deployment of product to customers has been achieved

This questionnaire is implemented through an Excel spreadsheet which also contains the algorithms used to score the answers given. The following section details how the TRL and MRL values will be calculated from the users' replies.

3.2 SWForum.eu MTRL Tool – The Scoring

As previously described, there are two sets of questions, one focused on obtaining the TRL (the first two questions) and the other on obtaining the MRL (the rest of the questions).

To obtain the TRL score, SWForum.eu MTRL tool uses the same criteria as the NYSEERDA tool: the value selected for PROJECT MATURITY determines the TRL between levels 1 – 5 and the value selected for PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT determines the TRL between levels 6 – 9. To be more specific:

- When the value of PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT is between 2 and 5, the TRL value is obtained proportionally to this value, regardless of the value of PROJECT MATURITY.
- When PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT is 1, the value of PROJECT MATURITY coincides with the TRL value.

Error! Reference source not found. shows how the scores are obtained from these two questions.

Table 4. TRL Score based on answers to questions 1 & 2

1. PROJECT MATURITY	2. PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	TRL
-	5	9
-	4	8
-	3	7
-	2	6
5	1	5
4	1	4
3	1	3
2	1	2
1	1	1

To explain with a mathematical expression, let q_1 be the value selected for the PROJECT MATURITY question and q_2 the value selected for the PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT question, then the final TRL score would be calculated using the expression:

$$TRLscore = \begin{cases} q_2 + 4, & (q_2 \geq 2) \\ q_1, & otherwise \end{cases}$$

To get the MRL score, the SWForum.eu MTRL tool follows a different approach. We assign each question a weight depending on which of the areas being question we believe is the most important right through to the one which is the least important for the assessment being completed. We have used the following considerations to establish the weight for each question:

- **Team:** Human assets are key for any organization. So, a well-organized group of people are most likely to lead a project to success.
- **Manufacturing/Supply chain:** Having an experienced sales mechanism will pave the entry of any product/service into the market. Starting to commercialise a product without previous experience is a difficult task.
- **Go to Market:** Business models enable an organization to create value out of new ideas. Simply having a good product or service is not enough without the answers to key questions about how to take it forward.
- **Product Definition / Design:** A good business model needs to be complemented by a well-defined product/service from the beginning, responding to the end user needs. If not, the brand name can be affected by the bad opinions about the product/service after what seemed like a successful product launch.
- **Competitive landscape:** With all the previous issues covered, success seems quite probable. But there is still a weak point that can affect the sales: a lack of knowledge of

the market in understanding and demonstrating that the product/service satisfies a need or requirement better than competitors.

- **Documentation:** Specifically for highly innovative R&D projects, including new technologies or new ways to apply technologies, there is a need to capture each step in the product/service development, from design to commercialization, because innovation means new ways of doing things, and everything must be highly detailed.
- **Intellectual Property Management:** Intellectual Property is one of the most important assets of a leading-edge technology organization. Therefore its management and the appropriateness of steps taken must be clear.

Error! Reference source not found. shows the weights assigned to each question in the scope of the cyberwatching.eu project.

Table 5. Weight of each of the questions

QUESTION	WEIGHT
3. PRODUCT DEFINITION/DESIGN	4
4. COMPETITIVE LANDSCAPE	3
5. TEAM	7
6. DOCUMENTATION	2
7. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT	1
8. GO-TO-MARKET	5
9. MANUFACTURING/SUPPLY CHAIN	6

To explain this by a mathematical expression, let q_i be the value of the answer to question i and w_i the weight of that question (for i from 3 to 9), then the score obtained according to the questionnaire would be $\sum(q_i \cdot w_i)$. Given that 5 is the highest possible value for each answer, the maximum value that could be obtained according to this questionnaire would be $5 \cdot \sum w_i$. Since what is intended is to obtain a value within the scale defined for MRLs, which has 9 values, the final MRL score would be calculated using the expression:

$$MRLscore = \frac{9 \times \sum(q_i \times w_i)}{5 \times \sum w_i}$$

To better understand the formula above, let's calculate the pair (TRL, MRL) for a real project included in the SWForum.eu project hub, the SODALITE [7]project.

We sent the questionnaire to a project representative of SODALITE, who provided the answers shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 6. MTRL Questionnaire responses from SODALITE project

1. PROJECT MATURITY
4. Initial testing of integrated product has been completed in a laboratory environment. Early prototype.
2. PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT
2. Pilot scale product has been tested in the intended environment close to the expected performance. Prototype System.

3. PRODUCT DEFINITION/DESIGN
3. The product has been scaled from laboratory to pilot scale and issues that may affect achieving full scale have been identified
4. COMPETITIVE LANDSCAPE
4. Competitive analysis to illustrate unique features and advantages of the product compared to competitive products has been completed
5. TEAM
2. Solely technical or non-technical founders running the organization with no outside assistance
6. DOCUMENTATION
5. Marketing documentation has been created, such as a Business Model Canvas, etc.
7. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT
4. An assignation of exploitation rights has been developed
8. GO-TO-MARKET
3. Market and customer needs and how those translate to product requirements have been defined, and initial relationships have been developed with key stakeholders across the value chain
9. MANUFACTURING/SUPPLY CHAIN
2. Relationships have been established with potential suppliers, partners, service providers and customers and the have provided input on product and manufacturability requirements

After applying the formulas for TRL and MRL using the weights of **Error! Reference source not found.**, its score would be:

- $TRL = 6$
- $MRL = \frac{9 \times [(3 \times 4) + (4 \times 3) + (2 \times 7) + (5 \times 2) + (4 \times 1) + (3 \times 5) + (2 \times 6)]}{5 \times (4 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 5 + 6)} = \frac{9 \times 79}{140} = 5.08$

Rounding down values, the score (TRL, MRL) is (6, 5).

From these two values we are then able to provide a single MTRL score. It has been decided within the SWForum.eu project that the MTRL value itself will be calculated using a simple product of the two values. Therefore, in this case, SODALITE has a MTRL value of 30.

The next step is understanding how we gave some simple recommendations to the project about what steps etc. are needed to improve their TRL & MRL scores.

3.3 SWForum.eu MTRL Tool – The Recommendations

Alongside the scoring that the project receives for TRL, MRL and MTRL, they also receive tailored high-level feedback as a one line piece of guidance or recommendation which is dependent on the scoring for their different questions.

3.3.1 TRL Recommendations

For each value of TRL that is given as a result of the assessment there is a simple recommendation for next steps as described below:

Table 7. Recommendations/Comments based on measured TRL scores.

TRL	RECOMMENDATION/COMMENT
1	"It seems you are still doing basic research. Next step is advancing to technology formulation."
2	"It seems that you already formulated the technology. It's time to advance to an applied research."
3	"You are doing applied research. Next step is validating your results in a controlled environment."
4	"You reached the prototype phase. If it is still an early prototype, next step is taking it on a large scale. If your MRL is over 4 you should use participation in the SWForum.eu Forum to publicise your activities."
5	"Your product/service has been proved in its prototype version in an intended environment. It is time to validate your results, so if your MRL is over 4 you could use contacts in the SWForum.eu Forum to find possible partners/users."
6	"Your project is in a validation phase close to the expected performance."
7	"Your project is being validated in an operational environment. You are in a pre-commercial phase. If your MRL is over 6 you think of using the SWForum.eu Forum to find customers to further exploit outputs."
8	"Your project is already a commercial system. You should join ensure the SWForum.eu Forum members are aware of this and that your entry on the Hub has links to your outputs."
9	" Your project is already a commercial system. You should join ensure the SWForum.eu Forum members are aware of this and that your entry on the Hub has links to your outputs."

3.3.2 MRL Recommendations

The recommendations here are not only dependent on score but also on how the score given has been achieved. As such there is a combination of what the actual MRL score is and what the answers to some of the questions were giving multiple different possible options for some aspects of the recommendations/comments:

Table 8. Recommendations/Comments based on measured MRL Scores.

CONDITION	RECOMMENDATION/COMMENT
MRL <= 4	"Your project results are not marketable yet. You still have a long way to go. You could start by improving..."

& Q5 <= 2	"...your team."
& Q5 != 2 & Q9 <= 2	"...your manufacturing/supply chain."
& Q5 != 2 & Q8 != 2 & Q8 <= 2	"...your Go to Market Strategy."
& Q5 != 2 & Q8 != 2 & Q8 != 2 & Q3 <= 2	"...the definition/design of your product/service."
MRL <= 6	Your project needs to improve some aspects of the preparation to market, but if your TRL is over 4 you could be ready to join the SWForum.eu End User Club for validating results.
MRL <= 7	Your project results are ready to be commercialized, but there is still room for enhancement and some aspects should be improved. If your TRL is over 6, think about the SWForum.eu Forum should be used for publicity of the near production nature of your outputs.
MRL <= 8	Your sales are going well and your product/service seems stable.

3.4 Representing MTRL Assessment Outputs

The main objective of the task to which this deliverable is associated is to facilitate better exploitation of the outputs of EC funded actions and to ensure that possible exploiters from outside the project/product are able to better assess the state of something that they may wish to base future activities on. As such we also utilised the MTRL value calculated for each project within the other method of project assessment/visualisation that SWForum.eu has available, the project radar as described in SWForum.eu Deliverable 2 [8]. where we have described the different visual degrees of freedom that we will be using. As part of this a key visual clue is the colour of the blip for which we have finalised a scoring is as follows:

Based on the numerical MTRL score, the blip will be coloured as follows within the SWForum.eu Radar allowing clear representation of status:

1. **Red** for scores below 25;
2. **Yellow** for scores between 25 and 45 (inclusive);
3. **Green** otherwise (46 and above).

4 MTRL Assessment and Webinars

Since the launch of the MTRL process within SWForum.eu and following three webinars hosted related to the MTRL methodology, we have collected 33 assessments so far from 24 projects. This includes several projects that completed multiple assessments at different stages of their lifecycle. The latest MTRL results from projects which have completed an assessment are shown here in Table 9.

Table 9. MTRL Assessments for supported projects as per 20/6/2023

PROJECT	CALL	1. PROJECT MATURITY	2. PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	3. PRODUCT DEFINITION / DESIGN	4. COMPETITIVE LANDSCAPE	5. TEAM	6. DOCUMENTATION	7. IP MANAGEMENT	8. GO-TO-MARKET	9. MANUFACTURING/SUPPLY CHAIN	TRL	MRL	MTRL
FISHY	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	4	2	7	6	42
SODALITE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	3	4	2	5	4	3	2	6	5	30
MEDINA	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	4	2	2	1	4	5	2	1	1	4	3	12
PIACERE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	2	3	3	5	3	3	1	4	4	16
ADMORPH	H2020-ICT-2018-20	2	1	1	0	2	1	2	0	0	2	1	2
AI SPRINT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	2	3	4	3	2	2	1	4	4	16
ARTICONF	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	2	2	4	1	2	1	1	3	3	9

CHARITY	H2020-ICT-2018-20	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	3	1	3
COSMOS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	5	2	1	2	5	4	5	4	2	2	5	5	25
DATA CLOUD	H2020-ICT-2018-20	3	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	3	3	9
DECODER	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	1	1	2	3	5	4	1	1	1	4	3	12
INFINITECH	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	3	4	2	3	1	2	1	1	6	3	18
INGENIOUS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	8	8	64
IOT-NGIN	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	1	2	4	4	5	4	3	0	0	4	4	16
MORPHEMIC	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	7	6	42
PHYSICS	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	3	3	4	5	2	2	1	1	6	4	24
SELENE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	3	1	1	1	2	4	3	1	1	1	3	2	6

SERRANO	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	1	1	1	4	4	0	1	0	4	3	12
TEACHING	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	1	2	1	2	4	1	2	1	4	3	12
UNICORE	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	2	4	4	4	5	3	3	2	6	6	36
VEDLIOT	H2020-ICT-2018-20	4	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	4	7	5	35
ASCLEPIOS	H2020-SC1-FA-DTS-2018-2020	4	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	4	2	8
POLICY CLOUD	H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2018-2019-2020	4	2	3	2	4	1	2	1	1	6	3	18
IOTAC	H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020	5	3	4	4	4	5	5	3	1	7	6	42

The graphs in Figures 2 and 3 show the MTRL assessments from different projects. Most of the projects with low scores only submitted a single assessment in the middle of 2022, which does not necessarily show the project's current status.

Figure 2. MRL and TRL Scores from supported projects as per 20/7/2023

Figure 3. MTRL Assessments from supported projects as per 20/7/2023

We also hosted our last webinar on Understanding the impact of MTRL Assessments at the beginning of June 2023 to demonstrate the progress certain projects have made since their inception. The three webinars conducted are available via Youtube and the SWForum webinar page:

- The MTRL Methodology: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LnRkbemsxmU&t>
- Understanding criteria for optimal self-assessment of project outcomes using MTRL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Er44RGXxz8>
- Understanding the impact of MTRL Assessments: <https://swforum.eu/events/understanding-impact-mtrl-assessments>

5 Conclusions

Having outlined the methodology that we use to obtain the TRL, MRL and MTRL values for outputs from projects that we are supporting, we have seen that there is a structural framework behind the assessments to ensure that we are able to not only get projects to self-assess but also conduct multiple assessments to track their progress, spaced appropriately through their lifetime. However, this is contingent upon projects choosing to participate in this activity and submitting a reassessment, which we observed was only done by 8 projects.

We feel that in contrast with earlier incarnations of the MTRL assessment that the sheer numbers of projects that were in the calls our CSA was supporting, and especially the number of ongoing projects was actually rather small. As such we would judge the engagement a success even though the absolute numbers of projects engaged was small.

Nonetheless, completing this assessment and the webinars allowed for projects to understand why the TRL and MRL scores are weighted the way they are to which they all agreed and offered constructive feedback through their personal experience of completing the assessment. The positive feedback and participation from projects demonstrate the benefit of producing more of such assessments in the future and adapting and reproducing this tool in similar settings.

As part of our feedback segment during the webinars, various projects complemented about the usability of the MTRL tool. One of the project coordinators wrote an email to us highlighting the usefulness of the tool.

“The MTRL assessment is an intuitive and helpful tool to monitor the state of a project from a technological perspective and from a market realm, providing us with a useful signal on the progress of the project in what regards highly relevant aspects that enrich the value proposition. It is a great exercise to assess in yearly cut-off dates with the consortium partners and have the opportunity to discuss further improvements taking into consideration the suggested options.”

With this positive outcomes from engagement by those projects that chose to do so we aim to publish the MTRL assessment framework in an open access repository alongside supporting documentation such that others may continue to build on our work.

6 References

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